

The Fragility of Human Knowledge

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Since the beginning of recorded history, knowledge has been repeatedly lost through war, disease, political collapse, and natural disasters. We always seem to lose knowledge one way or another. One of the most famous examples is the loss of The Great Library of Alexandria. That might be one of the single most devastating losses in our history to date regarding knowledge loss. Why? Because, not only did we lose all of what we had learned up to that point, we may never learn or relearn what was lost.

Oftentimes we think of the loss of language and think something like “we just lost a way to communicate”. That is true but it is not the whole story. What is overlooked is the stories, the science, the frameworks, building techniques we still cannot replicate, and much more. Empires rise and fall. Languages thrive and go silent. And we are producing knowledge faster than any other civilization in recorded history.

We have taken steps to solve the issues of our past. We have things such as digital storage systems. Very powerful, advanced even, but not resilient. We store all of our knowledge on one fragile planet. If we face another collapse, much of what we gained will be lost repeating the same pattern again from our past.

As we continue to thrive as a species we begin to take for granted how important knowledge preservation is and it does not advance along with everything else even though it is the reason we are here now living the way we are. I think exploration should grow together with preservation. There are three ways we can achieve this.

- Distributed archives throughout Sol in redundant locations designed to last long periods of time.
- A ringworld at the lagrange point between Earth and Mars
- Both

The main purpose of this would be to preserve the complete story of us and Earth's. What should be preserved?

- Earth's geological history
- Evolution of life
- Extinction events
- Human civilizations
- Mistakes and failures
- Wars and recovery
- Scientific progress

- Cultural achievements

Our mistakes are just as important as our success because they show why something failed. These archives should rely heavily on images, mathematics, and universal patterns. It should be understandable to us along with any other future civilizations far removed from our culture.

We are only a blink of an eye in the existence of our beloved home. Preserving this knowledge this way ensures that the story of life and our civilization is not lost.